

1 **Markers of infection in HCV+ kidney transplant recipients.**

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6 Availability of donor kidney for transplantation in cases of severe disease or trauma has increased with
7 availability of HCV+ donor tissue. We measured total transcription in the blood of transplant recipients at
8 one month post kidney transplantation. We observed specific activation of *Cmpk2*, *Rsad2* and *Samd9*, key
9 components of the HCV infection gene signature, in the whole blood of transplant recipients from HCV+
10 donors. We present the first transcriptome evidence that receiving organ transplant from a HCV+ donor is
11 associated with systemic HCV infection in the recipient.

12 Citations

13 1. Pol, S., Parlati, L. and Jadoul, M., 2019. Hepatitis C virus and the kidney. *Nature Reviews*
14 *Nephrology*, 15(2), pp.73-86.

15 GSE213705